

SUBTRACTIVE STRATEGIES FOR ARCHITECTURAL PERSISTENCE

The Land of Thousand Dances

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CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

Progressive disappearance of the structure built in Evian between 2019 and 2022. © Camille Fauvel

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Subtraction of elements used as part of a greenhouse in Evian and reused as panels and sits for a public space on the EPFL site. © Camille Fauvel (2022)

This contribution builds upon a series of pedagogical experiences initiated in 2021, under the name *The Land of Thousand Dances*¹, which have taken the form of annual one-week workshops for students in architecture, civil engineering, and environmental sciences at Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (CH)². These interdisciplinary workshops focus on care and maintenance of existing structures, they are led by architects, civil engineers, and landscape architects.

1 The course has been taught by Camille Frechou, Camille Fauvel and Julien Gamarro since 2021, then with Tiphaine Abenia since 2023. Over the years, Nicolas Rogeau, Vestartas, Laurent Chassot, Julien Lafontaine-Carboni and Ronan Schubnel have taken part.

2 The Land of Thousand Dances is part of the teaching unit *Projeter Ensemble* at ENAC, EPFL. It is addressed to second year students under the format of an intensive week. It is organized around two hours per week during five weeks followed by one full week of intensive workshop and welcomes students coming from three different sections : architecture, civil engineering and environmental science and engineering.

If traditional architecture education relies heavily on abstraction -where the site, program, actors are often part of idealized and hypothetical scenarios- these pedagogical experiments diverge by bringing the studio into direct engagement with the outside world. They foster a hands-on relationship with materials, territories, and people, while integrating the minimization of environmental impact and collaborative processes as essential components of the architect's curriculum. In this context, The Land of Thousand Dances can be positioned within a contemporary constellation of architectural education experiments that emphasize holistic, onsite, long-term and interdisciplinary interventions at full scale. Analog initiatives include the Garden project by the Studio Tom Emerson (ETH Campus, Zurich, since 2015), the From Building to Building experiment by NTNU as part of the Crafting Circularity European project (Trondheim, since 2023) or the Koshirakura Landscape Workshop by Shin Egashira (Koshirakura, Japan, 1996-2023).

These courses challenge conventional pedagogies in architecture by prioritizing site maintenance and social connections over the mere creation of objects.

Because these pedagogical experiments transform existing sites, rely on 1:1 interventions, and involve concrete ecosystems of actors, they allow us to highlight a close parallel between learning and designing, as well as between observing and transforming. In this regard, this contribution draws an analogy between these pedagogical transformations and critical architectural practices³. The workshops enable an iterative approach, capitalizing on the often-ambiguous conditions inherent in pedagogical contexts, including legal and normative frameworks. Intervention hypotheses are formulated through careful observations of site usage, climate effects, and the impact of time on the existing structures. They also reflect the needs expressed by users, owners and caretakers of project sites.

Once implemented,
the project serves as a
testing ground, resulting
in iterative and critical
interventions that hold the
potential for jurisprudential
projects.

³ For another inspiring teaching format that bridges pedagogy, practice and research and integrates subtractive strategies, see : L. Devlieger (collectif ROTOR), 2017, «Architecture in reverse», Volume No 51 – Augmented Technology, (Supplément Studio Rotor : Deconstruction), Jaap Bakema Study Centre, Het Nieuwe Instituut, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment TU Delft.

The long-term nature of this pedagogical experience allows for the observation and documentation of its tangible impacts over time. A key distinction should be noted here in comparison to other hand-on learning workshops and design-built studios that often culminate in the construction of pavilions, which are quickly dismantled at the semester's end. The Land of Thousand Dances workshops challenge this disposability in educational production, instead embracing a long-term approach supported by iterative interventions. In particular, the projects sketched out by the students at scale 1:1 not only generate discussions about the future of the sites, but also tend to be considered and literally integrated into more institutional projects that follow the workshops. By suggesting a reinterpretation of these pedagogical experiences as practice-based research, this contribution emphasizes the significant role of education in shaping the practice of tomorrow.

The Jardin public in Evian, 1st edition - 2021. © Camille Fauvel

Architecture Beyond Addition

Architecture has always been taught as a practice rooted in addition and accumulation⁴. The architect builds, expands, and adds new material layers. The subtractive approach, on the other hand, seems to be outside the scope of teaching and practice. The American architect and researcher Keller Easterling emphasizes this absence: “Still, methods for demolishing, imploding, or otherwise subtracting building material are not among the essential skills imparted to architects in-training. With the belief that building is the primary constructive activity, the discipline has not institutionalized special studies of subtraction”⁵. Yet, building always involves a form of subtraction. Constructing here requires extracting elsewhere⁶. Subtraction is not synonymous with passive absence, but rather speaks of an active engagement in the design process. In this sense, the architect must develop specific skills to consciously integrate subtractive approaches in design and construction. But there is even more to it: in the face of the environmental, climatic, and social emergencies we are encountering, the subtractive approach, which supports not the demolition of existing structures but their maintenance, rearticulation and “assemblage”⁷ through targeted deconstruction⁸,

4 Space Caviar, 2021, *Non Extractive Architecture*. On *Designing without Depletion*, V-A-C Press and Sternberg Press, Moscow and Berlin.

5 K. Easterling, 2014, *Subtraction*, *Critical Spatial Practice* 4, Sternberg Press, Berlin, p 7.

6 On the reciprocity of additive and subtractive logics merging “invisible landscapes where materials come [and] highly visible, urban landscapes where those same materials are installed”, see : J. Hutton, 2020, *Reciprocal Landscapes*. *Stories of Material Movements*, Routledge, London.

7 We borrowed here the notion of “assemblage” to Anna L. Tsing. See : A. L. Tsing, 2019, “When the Things We Study Resound to Each Other. Tools for Unpacking “the Material”, in *Anthropos and the Material* (P. Harvey, C. Krohn-Hansen and K. G. Nustad eds.), Duke UP, pp. 221-243.

8 The projects undertaken by the architect Lucien Kroll in the 1980s on neglected

offers a promising avenue for shaping non-extractive architectural practices.

The workshop *The Land of Thousand Dances* initially followed the evolution of a timber pavilion (derived from balloon framing) constructed by first-year EPFL architecture students in 2019, in Evian (FR), close to the Grange au Lac⁹. This project was initiated and led by the ALICE Laboratory, directed by Dieter Dietz and Daniel Zamarbide, in partnership with Evian Resort, owner of the concert hall. Originally intended to be temporary installations, dialoguing with the environment only for one summer, some of these structures were so carefully assembled and constructed that they became the foundation for a pedagogical experiment in maintenance as an ongoing design project.

In the workshops,
maintenance is central -not
as a static preservation of
the status quo, but as an
opportunity for ongoing
and critical adaptation.

European housing estates allow us to appreciate the difference between demolition and targeted deconstruction. In several competitions, Kroll opposed the demolition of these structures and proposed instead, in Gennevilliers, Clichy-sous-Bois, and Hellersdorf, selective reductions and localized demolitions to restore a human scale to these large housing complexes. See : « Changer l'image du Luth, ville de Gennevilliers, Hauts-de-Seine » in P. Bouchain, 2013, Simone et Lucien Kroll : une architecture habitée, Actes Sud, Arles, p. 253.

⁹ The Grange au Lac is a concert hall entirely built in wood by Patrick Bouchain between 1992 and 1993 and owned by Evian Resort.

This approach aligns with an understanding of care as a relational practice, crucial for rethinking architectural transformation. As political science professor Joan Tronto argues, care and maintenance can reconnect architectural design processes with users and the environment: “Because care emphasizes processes and relationships that extend back and forward through time, [...] applying care theory to architecture would involve making a fundamental shift in perspective: care does not view the completed “thing” – building, park, city zone, etc. – as its object. It starts instead with responsibilities to care, not only for this “thing,” or its creator, builder, or patron, but for all who are engaged in contact through this thing.”¹⁰ By embracing these relationships of social and material care, this approach brings people and their environment closer together, assigning value to time – a key dimension for any adaptive design process.

The pause caused by COVID-19 then provided the opportunity to launch a new course centered around this theme. The proposal was to create a one week workshop, taking place every year in May, to work on the pavilion, to maintain it and to critically examine the notion of authorship. During the inaugural edition of the course, in 2021, the original pavilion underwent care and redesign, evolving into a public garden structure through supportive operations and local deconstructions, thus extending its temporary status. In the subsequent 2022 edition, due to the need for the site to become a logistic site for renovating the concert hall, the site was entirely dismantled, and its

10 J. C. Tronto, 1993, *Moral boundaries: A political argument for an ethic of care*, Routledge, London, p. 28.

fragments transported and relocated for reuse on the EPFL campus. A small square and a courtyard, both little used and maintained, became landing places for the deconstructed fragments. There, redesigned and reassembled, the fragments maintained their role as new condensers for public areas. The third edition (2023) saw further reconfigurations and subtractive operations, leading to shifts in the meaning of the remaining parts. The final edition of this four-year cycle of transformations just took place (May 2024). It marked the transition of responsibility for the project's care and maintenance to the institution overseeing the site (EPFL VPT Durabilité¹¹) and students' associations using and activating it (PotaGR, Artiphys, Asar, etc). This edition was also about bringing together the disciplines of architecture and landscape architecture. It marked a new stage in the questioning of authorial status. Projects became increasingly modest, almost indistinguishable, and inseparable from the dynamics of the living.

This series of interventions, characterized by a range of additive and subtractive operations, converge in their ability to sustain the project's longevity over time. The present contribution is illustrated through photographs and graphic documents produced by students during the workshops themselves. Observing these visual documents highlights a peculiar aspect of the teaching approach in its relationship to anticipation and drawing practices. Here, drawing is used intensely as a medium for observation, for assessing existing conditions, and for monitoring the passage of time. While it can also serve as a more conventional design

11 VPT : Vice-Presidence for Durability. The head of the Environmental service is François Dupuy. We are closely interacting with his colleague, Vincent Constantin, landscape architect in charge of the campus.

tool, this is not an absolute requirement—some projects are conceived without relying on prescriptive preliminary drawings, instead employing a series of 1:1 tests directly evaluated on site. The drawings shared in this publication are not retrospective synthesis documents crafted for project communication. Rather, they are archived fragments of the process, compiled annually into a collective publication, which is then shared with the next cohort of students. Three subtractive strategies have emerged from these teaching experiments: (1) subtraction as a condition for extended lifespan, (2) subtraction as a way to unveil and articulate new potentialities, (3) subtraction as an exchange rather than an erasure. These insights have developed over the years, shaped by the course’s evolution. This evolution reflects not only pedagogical intentions—such as the aim to connect architectural dynamics with landscape methodologies and foster long-term relationships with local associations and stakeholders— but also from external circumstances. For instance, the client’s 2022 decision to vacate the land necessitated the relocation of the project, resulting in its swift disassembly and reinstallation on the EPFL campus. Additionally, the gradual diminution of wood resources over the years has steered the course towards more modest and precise interventions. In this context, the three subtractive strategies reflect both the progression of The Land of Thousand Dances educational framework and the lessons learned from navigating real-world intervention scenarios.

In the following paragraphs, each of these strategies will be illustrated through specific operations drawn from the four editions of the course.

1. Subtraction as a condition for extended lifespan.

This first strategy, which introduces shrinkage as a means to withstand the test of time, addresses a critical tension: to ensure the project's overall longevity, its weakest components may need to be either reinforced or deconstructed. This approach was applied during the Evian period. To extend the temporary lifespan of the original project (initially intended to last only a few months), non-functional or structurally unsound parts had to be removed. For instance, the structure supporting the movie screen was vulnerable to wind, which jeopardized the project's long-term viability. It was deconstructed to improve the chances of extending the lifespan of the other structures. A similar approach was used for another structure on the same site (1st edition), where harsh weather conditions had damaged wooden parts. Removing these damaged elements led to a complete redesign of the access to the structure, ultimately improving the overall project.

A close parallel can be drawn here with certain principles of vernacular architecture. In their book *What about Vernacular?*²², architects Justine Lajus-Pueyo, Alexia Medec, and Margot Rieublanc explore the constructive and ecological common sense that underpins traditional architecture in the Eastern United States. During their journey to study these constructions in situ, they document the architecture

12 J. Lajus-Pueyo, A. Medec, and M. Rieublanc, 2023, *What about Vernacular?*, Parenthèses, Paris

Fig. démantèlement partiel de la protostructure

Fig. fin du démontage, la partie restante en maquette de cohérence

Fig. démontage des cadres qui permettrait de constituer une nouvelle séquence de protostructure

Fig. démontage de l'armant de la fontaine

Strategy 1. Extension of a temporary status by withdrawing non-functional or structurally unsound parts : restructuring the access of the structure following the deconstruction of elements damaged by weather conditions, 1st edition - 2021. © Camille Fauvel and students documentation

of North American covered bridges and observe that certain parts of these bridges, those most exposed to the elements and prone to premature weathering, are designed to be easily dismantled and replaced. These protective components, intended for periodic removal, follow the technique known as “planching.” Here, enabling targeted removal also extends the lifespan of these covered structures “by as much as a hundred additional years”, the architects note.

We can expand this tension between transformation and permanence by shifting our focus from localized fragments to entire structures. This is exemplified in certain forms of traditional Japanese architecture, particularly temples that are regularly dismantled and completely reconstructed. A famous example is the Grand Shrine of Ise, which is entirely taken down every 20 years to make way for a new structure that faithfully replicates the same key features, gestures, and constructive techniques. In his book *Japan-ness in Architecture*¹³, Arata Isozaki reflects on this cyclical reconstruction, framing it as a cornerstone of traditional Japanese architecture. The rebuilding process (now in its 62nd iteration) is deeply rooted in the Shinto concept of *tokowaka*, which emphasizes the renewal of objects to preserve their prestige and pursue a sense of eternity. This practice also serves as a means of transmitting building techniques across generations. Here, once again, subtraction does not oppose longevity—it ensures it.

2. Subtraction as a way to unveil and articulate new potentialities.

This second strategy employs subtractive operations as key mechanisms for requalification. Its goal is to enhance structural legibility and expand the potential uses of an existing site. This approach was tested in the first edition of the course. Through precise deconstructions, reopening its facades, a concert place was gradually transformed into a more versatile public space. The deterministic program once attached to the original project was then reconfigured to accommodate a broader range of uses. In the subsequent editions (2nd, 3rd, and 4th) held on the EPFL campus, further interventions based on removal principles were carried out on site. These interventions addressed not only man-made structures but also living ones, such as plant networks. In one courtyard where the workshop took place, a metal framework had been installed during years 1970 to support the growth of a wisteria. Although the plant had thrived, lack of maintenance led to an accumulation of dead wood over time, resulting in a dense canopy and a dark, uninviting space. By clearing the canopy, removing the dead wood, and pruning the remaining branches, the intervention allowed sunlight to filter through, thereby restoring the quality of the space beneath. This connection between livability and subtraction was powerfully demonstrated by social anthropologist Christine Hugh-Jones. In her work

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Strategy 2. Enhancing structural legibility / reopening the range of potential uses : cleaning the wisteria canopy to allow sunlight to filter through and restore the quality of the spaces beneath, 2nd, 3rd and 4th editions - 2022-2024. © Camille Fauvel and students documentation

From the Milk River: *Spatial and Temporal Processes in Northwest Amazonia*¹⁴ she offers an anthropological lens on space-making in the Amazon. The clearing of the jungle to create new habitable spaces can be understood as a form of subtraction that reveals latent potential. Hugh-Jones argues that this act of clearing is both practical and symbolic, paving the way for the creation of new, meaningful environments.

Beyond *The Land of Thousand Dances* workshop setting, we also find echoes of this second strategy in contemporary design practices. In architecture, practices like Kosmos or BAST describe the initial step of their interventions on existing constructions as a process of removal designed to reveal and engage with the main structural elements. BAST articulates this subtractive approach as follows: “we consider that the essential elements of a building’s structure must be preserved, while the secondary elements are removed. This “purging” process, which we regularly implement at the beginning of a construction project, involves removing all the secondary work, the non-perennial, returning to the building’s fundamental essence, namely its load-bearing structure”¹⁵. Through these subtractive gestures, architects gain access to the underlying structure of the project, which becomes a strong basis for its further evolution.

14 C. Hugh-Jones, 1979, *From the Milk River: Spatial and Temporal Processes in Northwest Amazonia*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge and New-York.

15 T. Abenia and J. Taillieu in conversation with BAST, 2024, “Dealing with architecture”, 2G No. 89, p. 137

3. Subtraction as an exchange rather than an erasure.

This third category is based on the principles of interconnected vessels. Subtraction is seen not as mere disappearance but as an opportunity for relocation, reuse, and transformation. Indeed, once deconstructed, elements can be fragmented, displaced, relocated, and reinterpreted, participating in an ecology of reuse. In this approach, subtraction serves as a means to reorganize resources and incorporates movement as a fundamental dimension of architectural design.

A concrete example of element displacement coupled with a transformation of their original meaning, was evident in the later editions of *The Land of Thousand Dances* workshops (2nd, 3rd, and 4th editions). Polycarbonate panels, initially used as greenhouse enclosures in Evian (Editions 0 and 1) were removed, reused and repurposed as sliding panels to create mobile partitions within the EPFL courtyard (Edition 2). Similarly, a staircase from the original pavilion in Evian was dismantled in one piece, then cut in two and subsequently reinterpreted in various ways: as a plant shelf (Edition 2), a seating area (Edition 3) and scaffolding during the 2024 workshop (Edition 4). During the last edition, the students also lightened overloaded sites and moved subtracted elements to new underused sites, engaging in

Strategy 3. Displacing elements, transforming their original meaning : Reusing the polycarbonate panels used as envelopes for a greenhouse for creating mobile demarcations within a courtyard, 2nd and 3rd editions - 2022-2023. © Camille Fauvel and students documentation

a dissemination of the fragments. They subtracted and repaired broken elements that hindered use, while enhancing existing situations through their parasiting.

This strategy strongly resonates with contemporary discussions on circularity in architecture. In their *Compendium of Circular Architecture*¹⁶, Eva Stricker, Guido Brandi, and Andreas Sonderegger note that “for millennia, disused buildings have been cannibalized for the construction of new ones.” However, this practice was largely abandoned following industrialization, only to re-emerge today as a response to the urgent need to conserve increasingly scarce resources and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. On one hand, the concept of *urban mining*—the process of reclaiming and reusing materials from existing buildings rather than sourcing new ones from natural resources—reframes cities as material depositories to be tapped into instead of discarded. On the other hand, the idea of a *donor building*—a structure slated for renovation or demolition whose elements are salvaged and reused—extends the lifecycle of these materials, preserving their value and integrating them into new projects. Viewing subtraction as an exchange rather than mere erasure redefines the built environment as a dynamic, ever-evolving landscape where buildings are not static objects but ongoing events, open to interpretation and continuous transformation.

16 E. Stricker, G. Brandi and A. Sonderegger, 2022, *Reuse in Construction: A Compendium of Circular Architecture*, Park Books, Zurich

Challenging Authorship

Subtraction impacts not only the physical integrity of the structure but also challenges the perception of a finished, fixed object attributed to a single author. By reopening the project, subtraction disrupts traditional notions of authorship, inviting other actors to continue the design, maintenance and transformation of the structures. In his essay *The Poetics of the Open Work*, Umberto Eco highlights how the notion of “open work”, rooted in ideas of incompleteness and openness, allows for “countless different interpretations (...). Every reception is both an interpretation and a performance, because in every reception the work takes in a fresh perspective for itself”¹⁷. An open work, therefore, is not only open to diverse interpretations but also invites a multiplicity of authors to participate. When applied to the design of open structures in architecture, it highlights the capacity of certain constructions to adapt and evolve over time. The concept of “open building”, as theorized by Dutch Structuralism, refers to constructions that accommodate changing needs and actors throughout the building’s life. Such buildings leave room for choice and responsibility, empowering future occupants to actively shape their environments according to their needs and available resources. *The Land of Thousand Dances* extend this attitude, serving as a testing ground to carefully assess the capacity of built structures to adapt and evolve over time.

Openness also encourages a collaborative mindset, invit-

¹⁷ U. Eco, 1989, *The Poetics of the Open Work*, Chapter 1 “The Open Work”, Cambridge, p. 2 available online: https://20biennial.fundacionpaiz.org.gt/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Eco-Umberto_The-Poetics-of-the-open-work.pdf

ing a diverse range of stakeholders to engage in the design process. In this context, subtraction becomes a means of transmitting gestures over time. *The Land of Thousand Dances* teaching unit exemplifies this mindset by bringing a new cohort of students each year to care for, maintain, and build upon the work of their predecessors. This iterative approach positions openness as a core principle of architectural design, enabling projects to evolve organically over time. By welcoming students from diverse disciplines—architecture, civil engineering, and environmental sciences—and encouraging close collaboration with local actors, the course leverages collaboration as a powerful tool. It also recognizes that relinquishing some control over the project’s final outcome and future use can result in richer, more dynamic possibilities.

This process does not seek to erase the role of the architect but to reinvent it—an evolution that may even renew the architect’s sense of joy in the practice:

“Whatever the pleasures and prodigious efforts associated with erecting architecture, the art of causing it to disappear can be equally compelling or satisfying”¹⁸.

18 K. Easterling, 2014, *Subtraction*, Critical Spatial Practice 4, Sternberg Press, Berlin, p. 7.

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